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How participatory mapping can lay the foundations for *Smart Villages*

liminal shape rural futures

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1.1 Summary of the Action-Research¹

This report presents the results of the Weaving Urban Data research project, a participatory mapping initiative aimed at bridging the digital divide on rural mobility in Italy by increasing accessibility in small towns and laying the basic digital infrastructure for the Smart Villages² of the future. The project focused on developing a methodology to increase the availability of accurate geospatial data to improve navigation services, local tourism and residents' quality of life. The initiative addresses the disparity in digital data availability between urban and rural areas, which particularly affects digital mobility and access to geographic information. The lack of accurate geospatial data in rural regions hinders navigation, ride-sharing services, and home delivery, which are essential for residents and tourism. This project aims to equip the area of study with the basic digital infrastructure needed to make these services possible.

The objective of the research was to develop a scalable methodology for collecting navigation data, particularly in historic centers and villages. The developed methodology was directly field-tested in the Monti Prenestini area, in the historic centers of Capranica Prenestina, Castel San Pietro Romano, Guadagnolo and Rocca di Cave, focusing on their ZTOs³ A and B. During the fieldwork, the research team updated data for 1,145 addresses and mapped 11.28 kilometers of roads, completing the availability of metadata for navigation. The project achieved a 70% increase in available data and 100% coverage of road traffic information for roads in ZTOs A and B. The data was subsequently uploaded to Google Maps to make it easily accessible to visitors and easy to integrate by service providers.

The impact of these results goes beyond navigation. Comprehensive mapping promotes local tourism by helping visitors easily locate points of interest, accommodations, and other local attractions. More accurate data benefits both residents and businesses, creating opportunities for economic activity. It also makes essential services more accessible, facilitating home and emergency medical care, postal and courier deliveries, enabling more efficient services for residents.

¹ Lewin, Kurt. "Action Research and Minority Problems." *Journal of Social Issues* 2 (1946): 34-46.

² Smart Villages is a European Union rural development policy initiative that promotes the use of innovative and digital solutions to improve the quality of life, services and sustainability of rural areas. See: https://ec.europa.eu/enrd/smart-and-competitive-rural-areas/smart-villages_en.html

³ Homogeneous Territorial Zones (ZTOs) are territorial areas defined and subdivided by Italian urban planning regulations with the aim of regulating and planning land use. Introduced by Ministerial Decree No. 1444 of April 2, 1968, ZTOs establish different categories of zones within a municipal territory, distinguishing them according to their prevailing use and urbanistic characteristics. Zone A includes historic centers and agglomerations with buildings of historic or artistic value, which are often subject to conservation restrictions. Zone B, on the other hand, covers partially built-up areas where at least 12.5% of the area is occupied by existing buildings, generally characterized by a consolidated urban fabric.

A framework was also developed during the project to assess the feasibility and impact of future initiatives to further bridge the digital divide. Using an impact-effort matrix, the project prioritized future actions to ensure optimal resource allocation and maximize community benefits. In addition, automated data management and analysis methodologies were developed to ensure sustainability and replicability of these efforts on a national scale.

2.1

Challenge Results

Fig. 1

Summary of results achieved: total addresses updated and added, total new addresses, and total roads corrected and updated.

Total Addresses Mapped			
1145	Capranica Prenestina	414	+87.5% over existing
	Castel San Pietro Romano	341	+18.8% over existing
	Rocca di Cave	324	+87.5% over existing
	Guadagnolo	66	+87.5% over existing
New Addresses			
428	Capranica Prenestina	193	47% of the new total
	Castel San Pietro Romano	52	15% of the new total
	Rocca di Cave	151	47% of the new total
	Guadagnolo	31	47% of the new total
Number Of Correct And Updated Addresses			
717	Capranica Prenestina	221	53% of the new total
	Castel San Pietro Romano	289	85% of the new total
	Rocca di Cave	173	53% of the new total
	Guadagnolo	35	53% of the new total
Roads Corrected And For Which Essential Navigational Metadata Was Updated			
11.28 km			

In just one week of fieldwork, the research team's efforts resulted in the verification and updating of 1,145 homes and 11.28 km of roads. During the initial analysis, 717 homes were identified with unverified addresses, highlighting the existence of areas in need of further verification. By the end of the initiative, on the other hand, there were as many as 1,145 correct, new and verified addresses—a 70% increase over the baseline. With regard to the road network, street names, pavement data, speed limits, and access bans were integrated, resulting in 100% coverage of the road network in ZTOs A and B in the three municipalities, for a total of 11.28 km. The impact of these results on navigation data-dependent services is not yet fully measurable, but it is expected to lead to significant improvement in access to door-to-door, logistics and emergency services.

Fig. 2

Pre- and post-intervention representation of the search for a residential address in the Municipality of Rocca di Cave previously untraceable on Google Maps.

2.2

Contextual Overview

The digital mobility gap in Italy's rural areas

In Italy, there is a significant gap in the availability and accessibility of digital data between urban and rural areas. This phenomenon is particularly evident in digital mobility and access to geographic information in rural areas of the country, where the very morphology of historic centers prevents large-scale automated mapping, thus requiring new methods of data collection. The absence of up-to-date and accurate local data limits the effectiveness of many navigation platforms and digital services, creating obstacles for both residents and visitors and preventing the development of home-based services in the area. Many municipalities, especially those that are small or located in rural and mountainous areas, often do not have up-to-date digital geospatial data on roads and addresses even at the level of public administrations. This absence of accessible data negatively impacts local businesses by preventing them from taking full advantage of the opportunities offered by the digital economy, and the quality of life of citizens who lack essential home services.

The morphology of historic centers in rural areas contributes to the difficulty in mapping and navigation itself; dwellings resulting from layers of architectural interventions from different eras often have entrances on multiple fronts and alleys are difficult to access by vehicles, making mapping more difficult. In the municipalities of Castel San Pietro Romano, Capranica Prenestina, Guadagnolo and Rocca di Cave, only 63% of the addresses surveyed during the Weaving Urban Data initiative were already available on Google Maps, and many of these were incorrectly located due to a lack of basic street data. It is important to note that the total number of addresses in the three municipalities is unknown, so it is not certain that all inhabitable buildings were surveyed. In fact, with the exception of the municipality of Rocca di Cave, house address plates are often missing or incorrectly located, suggesting that 63% of the available addresses probably represent a smaller proportion than the actual total number of dwellings.

Fig. 3

Pre- and post-intervention representation of the search for a residential address in the Municipality of Capranica Prenestina whose geolocation was updated on Google Maps.

Collecting and making available high-quality digital data first and foremost facilitates movement and use of services in small communities, overcoming the current fragility of a system that relies primarily on the personal knowledge of local actors and informal relationships. This dependence on unstructured knowledge is a significant barrier to entry for new residents and entrepreneurs, precisely in territories that need to counter depopulation. Digitization of spatial data makes it possible to systematize this knowledge, making it accessible to all and not just those already integrated into the community, facilitating new residency. In addition, accurate data makes it possible to implement new mobility solutions in less connected areas such as

ride sharing, carpooling, and other on-demand transportation services. Reliable data make it easier for tourists to find and access places of interest, bars, stores, restaurants and agritourisms, helping to support local tourism and promote small independent businesses. Finally, with accurate data, it finally becomes possible to offer door-to-door services such as package delivery, grocery shopping, and health care, contributing to the well-being of the elderly and those with reduced mobility, as well as generally expanding the range of services offered to current and future residents.

Weaving Urban Data pushed further the Digital Paths Challenge⁴, conducted in 2023 in Monti Prenestini and part of the larger research conducted by Liminal in creating a layered approach to analyzing the physical and socio-economic landscapes of rural areas. During Digital Paths, the need emerged to add additional layers of information to public databases and wayfinding apps, particularly Google Maps. Liminal's projects involve the active participation of local communities, as in the case of the Digital Paths workshop, where community members contributed to data collection and mapping. Weaving Urban Data thus aimed to develop a scalable approach that simplified the data collection process and allow anyone in the future to contribute to their local area, even without advanced technical knowledge.

2.3

Methodological Approach

The methodological approach developed for the Weaving Urban Data research initiative consisted of three main phases: a preliminary research phase, a field testing and methodological development phase, and a data verification and feasibility assessment phase for future initiatives.

In the preliminary research phase, the goal was to establish the framework within which the research fits. This was accomplished by starting with the identification and quantification of the baseline of data present on the most widely used platforms, at the regional and municipal levels. In particular, data available on platforms such as OpenStreetMap, Google Maps and the Regional Geo-Topographic Database⁵, were analyzed in order to determine the existing coverage of streets, house numbers and points of interest (POIs). In parallel, research was conducted on the policy framework for digitization in the European context, funding opportunities for digitization initiatives in rural areas, and other examples of large-scale urban data and citizen science. Finally, case studies on existing data-driven participatory practices and the long-term potential of the initiative, including incentives and policies at the European Union level for Smart Villages, were explored.

⁴ Read more in the Digital Paths 2023 Challenge report

⁵ The Regional Geo-Topographical Database (DBGT) is the official digital map base representing all land features (buildings, roads, house numbers, etc.), made according to national technical specifications to ensure data interoperability and available in the same format in every region.

Fig. 4

Attributes identified for data collection and address loading during the preparatory phase.

Field	Required	Description
ST_NUM	Required	Street Number (i.e. house number, address number, etc.)
APT_NUM	Optional	Apartment Number
BLDGNAME	Optional	Building Name
ST_NAME	Required	Street Name and Type (Street, Avenue, etc., can be abbreviated but expansion of abbreviations is preferred)
NEIGHBH	Optional	Neighborhood Name
CITY	Required	City Name
STATE	Required	State (two-letter abbreviation)
ZIP	Required	5-digit ZIP code
CNT_NAME	Optional	County Name
CNT_FIPS	Optional	County FIPS 6-4 code (refer to Information Technology Laboratory)
ID	Preferred	A unique ID for the feature ⁶

In the second phase, the focus shifted to testing and developing the methodology in the field. The main objective was to develop a data collection approach that is easy to learn and implement in order to simplify the data collection and processing workflow. The methodology involves the use of the smartphone as a collection tool and a simple questionnaire with only text inputs. A system of codes assigned to streets and volumetric units allows only two numbers (that of the building and that of the access road) to be entered in addition to the data being researched (street name, house number, etc.). This approach allows the location of each address to be subsequently extracted in a highly accurate manner through an algorithm that uses the public datasets of the volumetric units and the street network surveyed in the field.

⁶ In GIS (Geographic Information Systems), the term "feature" refers to a geographic entity represented within a map or spatial database. A "feature" can represent a physical or conceptual object located in space, such as a road, river, building, administrative boundary or any other identifiable geographic feature.

Fig. 5

Attributes identified for data collection and road uploading during the preparatory phase.

Field	Required	Description
ID	Optional	A unique and stable identifier for the road segment
ST_NAME	Preferred	Street Name and Type (the words Street, Avenue can be abbreviated)
RT_NAME	Preferred	Route name
BIKE_RT	Preferred	Bike route name
ST_NM_A1	Optional	Alternative name 1
ST_NM_A2	Optional	Alternative name 2
NEIGHBH	Optional	Neighborhood name
CITY	Preferred	City name
ADMIN	Preferred	Highest level of administrative area
POSTAL	Preferred	Zipper code/postal code
AR_RT_FR	Optional	Starting address on the right-hand side, relative to geometry
AR_RT_TO	Optional	Ending address on the right-hand side, relative to geometry
AR_LT_FR	Optional	Starting address on the left-hand side, relative to geometry
AR_LT_TO	Optional	Ending address on the left-hand side, relative to geometry
SURFACE	Optional	Road surface
SPEED_LM	Optional	Speed limit in MPH or KPH
BIKE	Required	Whether the segment allows bikes, and if so, what route type it is
CAR_RESTR	Optional - unless a restriction is known	Whether the segment allows cars and trucks
PED_RESTR	Optional - unless a restriction is known	Whether the segment allows pedestrian use
DIR	Preferred	Identifies the direction of travel
BIKE_SAFETY	Optional - unless the route is known to have potential safety concerns.	Are there any known safety concerns with this bicycle route
SEPARATE	Optional	The road segment is separated by a barrier in the middle
TURN_R	Optional	Turn restrictions (below you'll find the exact format)
ELEV	Optional	If the road is elevated, or a bridge or tunnel

Fig. 6

Base map of the historical center of Rocca di Cave, made for field mapping.

The mapping process was carried out in two main steps. In the first step, data on streets and squares were collected by manually correcting or supplementing their geometry on the specially prepared base maps with available data obtained from the regional geoportale⁷. For each street, the name and data on accessibility, speed limits, and pavement were recorded through Jotform questionnaires⁸. These data were then integrated into a special GIS database, and maps were generated again with appropriate identification codes. In the second step, the individual house numbers were surveyed, assigning them the relevant volumetric units and streets through a

⁷ The accuracy of this method depends on the quality of the base map. It is preferred to use the volumetric units provided by the DBGT to ensure the scalability of the methodology in different regions, as these data are freely accessible throughout the country. Alternatively, when available, cadastral data can be used to ensure higher accuracy.

⁸ See <https://www.jotform.com/>

smartphone questionnaire. This two-step approach allowed a large number of addresses to be surveyed quickly, breaking down the process into simple steps and largely automating the geospatial restitution of the survey through a specially developed algorithm.

Fig. 7

Example of the Jotform forms developed for field data collection.

The image shows two smartphone screens displaying Jotform data collection forms. Both screens have a dark blue header with the text '< Weaving Urban Data -...' and a status bar at the top showing the time as 09:20 and 4G signal strength. The left screen is titled 'Address Points: Capranica Prenestina' and features a white form with the following fields: 'Building ID (See Basemap) *' with a text input box and the label 'ID Edificio (Vedi Mappa)' below it; and 'Street Code (ID) *' with a text input box and the label 'Codice Strada' below it. The right screen is titled 'Roads and Paths: Castel San Pietro Romano' and features a white form with the following fields: 'Road ID (Note on basemap while drawing) *' with a text input box and the label 'ID strada (nota sulla mappa di base durante il disegno)' below it; and 'Street Name and Type (eg. Via, Vicolo ...)' with a text input box.

The data collected in the field were then processed automatically using a Python algorithm, which allowed addresses to be geocoded by associating building *IDs* with street *IDs* and generating geospatial files. The algorithm extracted the centroids of the individual volumetric units, constructing at the centroid location a point for each address surveyed with the same metadata as the entry entered in the survey. For each address, the nearest point on the line of the corresponding road and the point of intersection between the perimeter of the volumetric unit and the connecting line with the reference road were identified. The point representing the address was then moved to the location identified through the intersection, thus obtaining the location of the address on the correct building frontage, with an accuracy relative to the accuracy of the survey of the individual housing units in the base map.

In parallel with the development of the data mapping and processing methodology, a framework for assessing the feasibility and impact of possible subsequent digitization or replication initiatives of the same initiative was also developed.⁹ This framework is based on the identification of key project partners for future initiatives and a structured approach to evaluating project ideas based on an impact/effort matrix. The methodology included key steps

⁹ See Annex 3.1.3 for the preliminary feasibility analysis done on possible future initiatives.

such as identifying stakeholders, defining needs and opportunities, categorizing opportunities, constructing an impact matrix, and evaluating outcomes. Opportunities were evaluated according to clear criteria, considering impact (high if the benefit involves multiple subgroups or the entire community, low if it involves only a single group) and effort required (high if implementation requires significant resources, low if it requires few resources and can be completed in the short term). The matrix made it possible to identify actions that offer the greatest benefit with minimal investment, facilitating optimal management of available resources.

Fig. 8

Analysis of geocoded addresses: Identification of centroids for each volumetric unit, connection of individual points generated in the centroid with the nearest point on the reference road, and geocoding of individual addresses at the point of intersection of the centroid-road connection line and the perimeter of the volumetric unit.

In the third phase, the focus was on verifying the data collected in Monti Prenestini, the territory where the methodology was tested, and uploading it to Google Maps through Liminal's accreditation in the Google Maps Content Partners program. The impact framework and feasibility assessment methodology for future initiatives was also refined. To ensure accuracy, the data validation process consisted of two main phases: a first phase of verifying and cleaning the data before processing, resolving any ambiguities in house numbers or street names; and a second phase of visually examining the results after processing, comparing the generated lines and points to verify the alignment of contiguous street segments with the center of the building, checking a random sample of 15% of the addresses for discrepancies. The verified data, already automatically formatted in a way compatible with the data structure of major wayfinding services, was directly uploaded to Google.

2.4

Challenges and Limitations

Although through its achievements the Weaving Urban Data project made significant progress, several challenges and limitations emerged during the course of the initiative. One of the main challenges was the inability to upload large amounts of data to OpenStreetMap, an open source wayfinding platform to which the research team planned to contribute collected data because it provides baseline data to a large number of service providers. Indeed, its open source infrastructure allows anyone to use the uploaded data. However, the limitations of the platform necessitated an overly manual approach that was not in line with the ambition to build a scalable method.

A second limitation concerns the accuracy of the data, as it is closely related to the quality of the volumetric unit data available in the base maps. In future interactions, cadastral base files provided directly by the relevant regional government, at the request of the relevant municipal agencies, could be used as they are generally more accurate than those available on the Regional Geoportal.

Although the project has produced clear benefits, measuring direct economic impact remains difficult. The lack of a clear methodology to quantify these impacts makes it more difficult to fully articulate the economic value generated (despite observable positive changes in accessibility and service delivery). Finally, the demonstration of direct economic impact is also critical in terms of the ease of scaling up the initiative, which while ready to be piloted on a territorial scale still has critical impact measurement issues that need to be resolved in order to apply the method on a regional and national scale. Additional forms of collaboration with partners such as Google Maps could help overcome this limitation by providing baseline data on economic impact that would allow modeling of results for future initiatives.

2.5

Conclusions

The Weaving Urban Data project successfully demonstrated the potential of participatory initiatives to address the digital divide in rural areas. Fieldwork has resulted in the updating of 1,145 addresses and the mapping of 11.28 km of roads, with a 70% improvement in the accuracy and availability of geospatial data. These updates have a direct impact to be measured in the long run on the accessibility of essential services, supporting local economic

development through tourism and improving the quality of life for residents.

The feasibility assessment framework is another tool to guide the decision-making process for initiatives, enabling a structured approach to prioritizing actions based on community needs and available resources. Finally, the methodologies developed for data collection, management, and analysis were critical to the success of the project and proved to be scalable and adaptable to similar rural settings. These approaches ensure that data collection is not only accurate but also sustainable, involving community members at every stage to ensure data accuracy. The methodological tools developed now make it possible to imagine this type of mapping on a national scale, promising to quickly bridge the geospatial data gap between rural and urban areas and providing a basic digital mobility infrastructure for small municipalities.

3.1

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3.1.5 Excel Table of Location of the Surveyed House Numbers
